

SELF-ORGANIZED TRAVEL: RESEARCHING THE TRENDS AMONG YOUTH IN HO CHI MINH CITY, VIETNAM

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Abstract

A survey on global travel trends in 2018 conducted by Visa revealed that 72% of Vietnamese people travel to experience different cultures, explore exciting destinations, and create opportunities for bonding with friends, family, or enjoying personal leisure time. In light of these purposes, self-organized travel is becoming increasingly popular, especially among today's youth, who are embracing this trend. Factors such as the growth of digital technology, societal and personal influences seem to be positively shaping the trend of self-organized travel among the youth of Ho Chi Minh City. Of particular note is the development and application of digital technology, which is enticing young people to actively participate in this trend. Digital platforms and data will play a significant role in booking travel arrangements online. For the youth, smartphones are essential tools for travel planning. The entire process of planning a trip, from booking accommodations and tickets to arranging tourist services and seeking information about travel destinations, is facilitated through information technology and social media. While not the sole determining factor of this trend, digital technology holds paramount importance in influencing the trend of self-organized travel among the youth of Ho Chi Minh City, serving as a precursor to its future development.

Keywords: Self-Organized, Travel, Trends, Youth.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism among the youth is booming and represents a promising niche for the development of Vietnam's tourism industry. According to UNFPA, Vietnam is currently in a demographic golden age, with the youth population (aged 15 to 29) accounting for nearly 30% of the total population, making it the largest demographic group in the country. Numerous reports and data worldwide affirm that the youth, or young adults, are considered the most potential-rich generation for tourism, as they have a strong inclination for exploration and are willing to spend generously on travel experiences [7]. Tourism among the youth is distinctive due to the unique nature, psychology, and motivations of young travelers. Young travelers are less focused on spending on typical tourism products and services. Instead, they travel to satisfy their emotions and engage in physically experiential activities. In Southeast Asia, a significant portion of young tourists opt for backpacking or adventure travel with the purpose of "traveling for experiences" and embracing new values [5]. Therefore, this demographic group deserves special attention and exploration from tourism scholars and professionals.

1.1. Overview of the Self-Organization Trend in Tourist Travel

1.1.1. Theoretical Background of the Trend

According to the Vietnamese Dictionary, a "trend" is a tendency or direction in the course of an activity. From a psychological perspective, individual psychological characteristics mainly differ through a few fundamental elements, one of which is the concept of trends. In this context, a trend is the inclination toward a particular goal or object. It is the system of inner factors that drive a person's positivity in their actions. This concept indicates that human trends reveal their desires, developmental directions, and what motivates them to pursue specific goals.

Expressions of Trends

Human trends are expressed through needs, interests, ideals, worldviews, and beliefs – these are the driving forces behind behavior and actions.

Needs: As A.G. Covaliop once said, "Needs are the requirements of different individuals and social groups, seeking specific conditions for life and development." Human needs are diverse and encompass two basic categories: natural needs and social needs. When needs are satisfied, individuals feel content, comfortable, and enthusiastic. Conversely, when needs are not met, people may feel frustrated, discontent, and irritable. Therefore, needs are the source of positivity, motivating human actions.

Interests: Interests represent an individual's unique attitude toward certain objects or phenomena, which have significant meaning in their life and evoke pleasure. Like needs, interests are also a driving factor, providing motivation for individual actions. When someone is interested in something, they can concentrate at a high level due to their passion and attraction to the subject. Hence, interests are a motivating force that leads to highly effective actions.

Ideals: Ideals are high, beautiful goals, idealized images that captivate individuals and provide a sense of direction. Ideals are constructed from full awareness combined with emotions and strong willpower, which gives individuals extraordinary strength to overcome difficulties, obstacles, and even sacrifice to achieve their goals. Ideals represent the highest concentration of personal trends, serving as a compass for personal development, directly influencing and controlling all human activities, and shaping the formation and growth of individuals.

Worldviews: Worldviews are an individual's system of views on nature, society, and themselves in the world, determining a person's guiding principles for action. Worldviews play a vital role in shaping an individual's thought processes and actions. They also reflect the theories and generalizations of the views and activities of a social group. "The more complex a set of events, the more numerous and varied the new ideas, the more urgently the need for a coherent worldview becomes." (M. Plank)

Beliefs: Beliefs are a quality of one's worldview, a crystallization of a system of views, knowledge, emotions, and will that individuals test and solidify as enduring truths in their lives. Belief becomes an individual's reality. People act based on their beliefs, and personal beliefs

can empower individuals to overcome any obstacle.

Concept of the Self-Organization Trend in Tourist Travelers

From the concepts of "trend" and the idea of self-organized tourist trips, we can understand this as a trend that tourists aspire to, encouraging them to pursue the goal of organizing and designing their own travel experiences without predefined constraints or arrangements. Therefore, the research group introduces the concept of the self-organization trend in tourist travel as the primary tool for their research:

The self-organization trend in tourist travel refers to the desire of tourists to pursue independent, experiential, and personally designed travel experiences.

Tourist Self-Organization Behavior

The self-organization trend in tourist travel reflects the behavior of tourists who, instead of opting for organized tours through travel agencies or tour companies, choose to self-organize and design their own trips based on their abilities and preferences.

This behavior is conscious and involves perception, attitude, and the choice of travel methods to satisfy the needs of tourists. Tourists have a clear understanding of their choices. They know what they like, what they want, and what they need to do. In other words, the choice of travel method is driven by clear motivations and specific purposes. Tourists have a profound understanding and appreciation of the significance of self-organized travel, as well as the value of selecting and using travel services during their journeys.

Currently, there are several research works related to consumer choice behavior in tourism. For instance, the consumer behavior model in tourism proposed by Engle, Kollat, and Blackwell (1968) outlines that the individual decision-making process in tourism includes eight stages: Need recognition, Priority setting for travel needs, Assessment of the commitment of time, money, and effort in the decision process, Information search, Evaluation and selection, Decision-making, Purchase and consumption behavior, Post-consumption attitudes. The consumer behavior model in tourism by Mathieson & Wall (1982) presents five stages in the consumption process: Need/wish to undertake the trip, Information gathering and evaluation, Decision-making for the trip, Preparing the itinerary, Post-trip satisfaction evaluation.

These models all emphasize that the choice process for tourist travelers begins with needs. It can be observed that the behavior of self-organizing tourist trips also originates from the tourists' own needs. Travel needs (or travel motivations) are the desire of individuals to visit a place different from their usual residence to experience new emotions, new experiences, new knowledge, to develop social relationships, rejuvenate, and achieve mental comfort. Travel needs are a unique and comprehensive type of human need, formed and developed on the basis of both physiological needs and psychological needs. When choosing to self-organize their travel, tourists have psychological needs such as self-affirmation, self-experience, and making new acquaintances.

1.2. Factors Influencing the Self-Organization Trend in Tourist Travel

1.2.1. The Development and Application of Digital Technology

It's undeniable that the remarkable development of technology has dominated various fields and global economies. As technology advances, so does the tourism industry, adapting with smart travel options and the integration of technical solutions in all operational processes to create the most attractive and appealing travel products for customers.

Tourists, especially the younger generation, are highly responsive to technology. They are eager to learn, adapt, and explore ways to leverage technology in their daily lives and independent travel experiences. Instead of purchasing expensive packaged tours, they consider why not travel independently, with more cost-effective options and greater autonomy, thanks to modern technology. They can easily research attractive destinations, select suitable means of transportation, and navigate to their destination using tools like Google Maps. They can independently book accommodations, restaurants, hotels, flights, and numerous other services through various smart applications. Consequently, their trips become much more convenient, all thanks to the smart application of digital technology. This is why the trend of self-organized travel is on the rise among young travelers.

The research group builds upon the work of Anna Polukhina, Anna Tarasova, and Avdykerim Arnaberdiyev in their paper "Information Technologies: Leading Innovative Factor for the Development of Independent Tourism" (2020). Additionally, research by Nguyen Thi Van Hanh and Nguyen Huu Binh in their study on the trends of technology application in tourist behavior, published in the journal "Development of Science and Technology - Social Sciences & Humanities," highlights the levels of technology application in various tourist behaviors, including information search, tour booking, travel services, on-site experiences, and sharing about their journeys. Furthermore, research by Pham Thi Thuy Nguyet outlines five prerequisites for the trend of personalized tourism, including: global information connectivity, the development of big data, the impact of online transaction software, mobile trends, and the online proficiency skills of young people.

1.2.2. Characteristics of Self-Organized Tourism

In the article "Self-tourism as an Alternative to Organized Tourism: Benefits, Challenges, Threats" by Volodymyr Antonenko and Volodymyr Khutkyi (2018), the concept of unorganized tourism, also known as amateur tourism, is discussed. Unorganized tourism refers to trips carried out independently by citizens without pre-booking tourism services or involving any intermediaries. Travelers who engage in unorganized tourism build their travel itineraries, select tourist attractions, determine the number of nights to stay, and pay for each tourism service (accommodation, meals, etc.) at the time of consumption. Scholars use the term "unorganized tourism" to describe trips organized by travelers themselves, without the involvement of travel businesses. Travelers who engage in unorganized tourism are guided by amateur principles and self-service (Antonenko, 2018, pages 101-107).

Independent travel has several appealing characteristics, especially for young people. Independent trips are often much more cost-effective compared to organized tours or expeditions, allowing travelers to extend their journeys with the same budget. Most activities that are organized during a trip can be done domestically at a lower cost when travelers arrange events themselves. Independent travel offers a high degree of freedom. Travelers can wake up whenever they want, go wherever they want, and do whatever they want. If they wish to continue meeting interesting people or exploring fascinating places, they can stay for weeks or longer, without being constrained by a fixed itinerary.

Independent travel provides unlimited opportunities to choose companions, interact, and make friends with strangers. It allows for meeting more people along the way. In independent travel, there's no need to stick with the same group of people for a fixed period of time.

These characteristics translate into advantages such as freedom, independence, flexibility, and cost-effectiveness, which drive the motivation of young people to undertake self-organized trips.

1.2.3. Family and Society

Family plays a significant role in shaping an individual's fundamental beliefs, perceptions, and decisions. Especially for young people, even though they are legally adults and responsible for their own actions, the thoughts, perceptions, and opinions of parents, siblings, or sometimes "permission" can strongly influence their decisions. Many young, dynamic students who are eager to learn and explore may want to undertake independent travel, but their parents may oppose it, citing reasons such as "you're not mature enough" or "it's too dangerous." The concerns of parents are valid, but individuals cannot remain within the safety of their family's nest forever. We need to step out, learn, and experience on our own, and traveling independently is an ideal activity for personal growth. Thus, family is a significant factor that can either encourage or discourage young people from self-organizing their travel.

Society, on the other hand, is a diverse environment with numerous factors that can strongly influence an individual's decisions. Building on the article "Travel and Social Media in China: From Transit Hubs to Stardom" published in the journal "Tourism Planning & Development" in October 2013, author Anders Ellemann Kristensen researched how the concept of self-organized tourism in China was shaped by tourists' interaction with social media. The first bloggers used travel to showcase their uniqueness, establishing a connection between promotion and social media. In Vietnam, young people spend a lot of time using social media platforms such as Facebook, Zalo, TikTok, Instagram, and more. They easily grasp any travel trend. Various groups, fan pages, YouTube channels, blogs, and music videos about travel are created, and members of these groups, along with followers of these pages, share posts, photos, and videos about travel, local cuisine, cultural beauty in different regions, and more. These contents are promoted, shared, and spread through social media, inspiring many young people who desire to travel and have personal experiences. This phenomenon is the result of the psychological contagion spread by social media.

1.2.4. Personal Factors of Travelers

The ultimate decision to undertake any action, including self-organized travel, lies with the individual. The decision to engage in self-organized travel is no different. Firstly, travelers must have a desire to travel. They may genuinely desire to travel to experience, learn, and gain various benefits, or they may simply follow what others are doing. This is an important consideration, as author Ma Quỳnh Hương pointed out in her article on the trend of "Phượt" among young people in Vietnam.

Furthermore, travelers' personal decisions are influenced by various objective factors, such as cost considerations, their ability to cover expenses, the ideal duration of the trip, whether they want to travel alone or with a group, safety concerns, and more. Travelers need to weigh all these factors before deciding to self-organize their trips.

The basic motivation for youth travel, as pointed out by authors Kadir Çakar and Faruk Seyitoğlu, is learning, meeting new people, enhancing career development, understanding different cultures, personal development, education, and travel being considered an essential part of young travelers' identity (UNWTO 2011; Demeter & Brátucu, 2014; King & Gardiner, 2015).

In the research paper "Travel decisions of students at a US university: Segmenting the international market" by Kakyom Kim, Giri Jogaratnam, and Jeonghee Noh, the authors identified seven push factors and six pull factors that express students' travel motivations. The push factors that drive students to visit predetermined destinations include a change of scenery, curiosity and learning, adventure and excitement, improving relationships, self-assertion, natural landscapes, and enjoyment and entertainment.

People, in general, have the need to travel to explore, experience, learn, connect with others, relax, relieve stress, bond with family and friends, and more. However, young individuals today, in addition to these fundamental needs, desire to affirm themselves, elevate their personal reputation and value, and develop their own identity. They have a need for independent activities, independent thinking, control over various aspects, a desire for adventure, challenges, and to become more courageous, self-reliant, and responsible for their own actions. Thus, self-organized travel satisfies these needs comprehensively.

1.2.5. Value Obtained from Self-Organized Tourism

Travel brings about numerous benefits and positive values for individuals. As a result, travel has become an essential need in various social strata. Emerging travel trends are likely to bring new and positive values.

The article "Self-tourism as an Alternative to Organized Tourism: Benefits, Challenges, Threats" by Volodymyr Antonenko and Volodymyr Khutkyi (2018) highlights the advantages of independent travel compared to organized tourism programs. Independent travel offers new skills and experiences. Independent travel is a challenging task, but, like any challenge, it is rewarded accordingly. Travelers who self-organize their trips immerse themselves in the whirlwind of travel and related issues, quickly gaining excellent experiences in time

management, communication with strangers, and language skills. A solo journey can be the ultimate test of self-confidence and self-reliance. Immersion in local culture is also a significant benefit. Independent travelers have more opportunities to interact with local residents wherever they go, whether it's in small cafes, shopping at local night markets, or discussing Buddhism with local monks. The opportunity to understand local culture significantly increases when traveling alone.

Author Ma Quỳnh Hương pointed out the significance and positive values of the "Phượt" trend among young people in Vietnam. "Phượt" carries fresh, progressive ideas and has a positive impact on the community, attracting many young participants. "Phượt" can provide participants with many exciting and beneficial experiences, starting with personal enjoyment, perception, and exploration of the beauty of the country, its culture, and its people. It helps individuals discover themselves, become more resilient, independent, and fosters teamwork. Nothing can awaken hidden potential better than an adventurous journey. When you have to take responsibility for your survival, you suddenly become more courageous, smarter, more resilient, and more flexible than you are in your daily city life. "Phượt" also serves as a way to relieve stress. These young adventurers have a need to explore new territories, even those that have never been touched by urban footprints, to seek a change, find reasons to live, and challenge themselves. Alongside "Phượt," the community has engaged in charitable activities, donating old books, clothes, and more to children in remote mountainous areas when traveling to these distant and desolate regions. Thus, beyond satisfying personal needs, it's a community-building endeavor. Sharing doesn't make them poorer; instead, it enriches their knowledge and emotional life in daily life and throughout each journey.

1.3. Proposed Research Model and Hypotheses

1.3.1. Proposed Research Model

H1: The "Development and Application of Technology" factor

H2: The "Characteristics of Tourism Types" factor

H3: The "Social" factor

H4: The "Personal" factor

H5: The "Value Received" factor

1.3.2. Research Hypotheses

H1 - The "Development and Application of Technology" factor has a positive impact on the trend of self-organized travel among young people in Ho Chi Minh City.

H2 - The "Characteristics of Tourism Types" factor has a positive impact on the trend of self-organized travel among young people in Ho Chi Minh City.

H3 - The "Social" factor has a positive impact on the trend of self-organized travel among young people in Ho Chi Minh City.

H4 - The "Personal" factor has a positive impact on the trend of self-organized travel among

young people in Ho Chi Minh City.

H5 - The "Value Received" factor has a positive impact on the trend of self-organized travel among young people in Ho Chi Minh City.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1. Research Measurement Scale

Table 1: Research Measurement Scale

Development and Application of Digital Technology	
CN1	Booking tickets and services via phone, iPad, laptop, etc.
CN2	Searching for travel destinations through tourism websites and social networks
CN3	Using map apps, translation tools for assistance
CN4	Globalization on social media platforms to expand connections and sharing
Characteristics of the Type of Travel	
DD1	Low cost
DD2	Freedom and independence in planning the trip
DD3	Flexibility in time and mode of transportation
Social Factors	
XH1	Influence from family and friends
XH2	The emergence of groups and clubs organizing trips
XH3	Feedback from people who have self-organized travel trips
XH4	Influence of crowd psychology
Individual Factors	
CN1	Individual skills and experience in organizing trips
CN2	Willingness to pay
CN3	Desire for self-affirmation
Values Obtained	
GTND1	Experience, knowledge, skills
GTND2	Expansion of social relationships
GTND3	The value of self-perception and understanding
Trends	
XuH1	If I do plan a future trip, I will opt for self-organizing
XuH2	Self-organized travel suits my current selection trends
XuH3	Generally, self-organized travel is my first choice currently

2.2. Survey Questionnaire Design

The survey questionnaire is completed after constructing and selecting the scales, as described in the process outlined in the diagram above. Ultimately, the completed questionnaire consists of three main parts:

Introduction Section: This section includes an introduction explaining the purpose and significance of the research and an invitation to participate in the survey.

Main Content Section: This section comprises questions designed based on the research model and scales that have been studied. Respondents will mark the most appropriate answer that reflects their level of agreement with the statements. The questionnaire questions are primarily designed as closed-ended questions for the convenience of respondents (quick and easy to answer). Additionally, this format facilitates data collection, processing, and analysis by the author. The Likert 5-point scale is used to measure the observed variables in the research model. Question 1 assesses the level of evaluation of technology development and digital application, question 2 pertains to the characteristics of the type of tourism, question 3 focuses on social factors, question 4 deals with personal factors, and question 5 relates to the perceived value.

Demographic Information Section: In this section, respondents will be asked to provide personal information to accurately identify the respondents as the correct target audience. Other information collected in this section aids in statistical analysis and provides additional insights into research issues. For categorical variables such as gender, occupation, age, and the most influential factor affecting the respondents themselves, measurement is done using identifying or ordinal scales, depending on the nature of the data reflecting these variables.

2.3. Determining the Sample Size

Research Population: The research population consists of all young people aged 16-30 who are living, studying, and working in Ho Chi Minh City.

Sampling Method and Sample Size:

Sampling Method: Conducting a survey of the entire population with a large scale is infeasible for most research studies. Therefore, selecting a sample is a more practical approach. To achieve the research objectives of this project, given limitations in financial resources, time, and a lack of comprehensive information about the entire population, a convenient non-probability sampling method was chosen. This method was chosen because the research team did not have a specific list of the entire population, and because the survey was conducted online without direct access to the research subjects. To ensure the representativeness of the sample, the research team attempted to select sample units that were students studying at various educational institutions in Ho Chi Minh City.

Sample Size: According to Comrey & Lee (1992), they suggest sample sizes with corresponding perspectives as follows: 100 = poor, 200 = fair, 300 = good, 500 = very good, 1000 or more = excellent. Other researchers propose sample sizes following the rule of thumb "multiply by 5" (Bollen, 1989), which means that the sample size should be at least five times the number of observed variables to ensure the reliability of the study.

The sample size for this research was determined based on the requirements of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Multiple Regression analysis.

For Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA): Referring to Hair, Anderson, Tatham, and Black (1998) for an estimated sample size, the minimum sample size is five times the total number of observed variables. This is a suitable sample size for studies using factor analysis (Comrey, 1973; Roger, 2006). $n = 5 * m$, where m is the number of questionnaire items.

For Multiple Regression Analysis: The minimum sample size required is calculated using the formula $n = 50 + 8 * m$ (m: number of independent variables) (Tabachnick and Fidell, 1996). Please note that m represents the number of independent factors, not the number of independent questionnaire items.

In this study, the research team chose a sample size that satisfied both of these formulas, which resulted in a minimum sample size of $n = 50 + 8 * 5 = 90$.

2.4. Quantitative Research

2.4.1. Preliminary Quantitative Research:

A preliminary quantitative study was conducted with a small number of participants (10 students) using a convenient sampling method. The purpose of this preliminary research was to standardize and refine the survey questions for clarity and convenience for the respondents. After conducting this preliminary research, the basic structure and content of the survey were accepted, and only minor adjustments were made to the wording of some questions to ensure that respondents did not misunderstand the content of the questions.

2.4.2. Formal Quantitative Research:

After establishing the research model and selecting and setting up the measurement scales for the variables in the model through qualitative research, a small-scale preliminary study was conducted to validate the measurement scales. Subsequently, formal quantitative research was carried out with the defined target group of respondents. In essence, the formal quantitative research was conducted with the predetermined research subjects.

3. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

3.1. Overview of Ho Chi Minh City

Introduction to Ho Chi Minh City: Ho Chi Minh City, also known as Saigon, is located in the southern part of Vietnam. It is approximately 1,730 kilometers by road from the capital city of Hanoi. Furthermore, the city is situated about 50 kilometers from the eastern coastline when measured by aerial distance, making it easily accessible.

Geographical Location: Ho Chi Minh City holds a pivotal geographical position in Southeast Asia, serving as a vital transportation hub for road, water, and air traffic. This strategic location has connected the city to various provinces within the region and established it as an essential international gateway.

Geographical Features: The geography of Ho Chi Minh City is characterized by its transitional location between the Southeastern region and the Mekong Delta. The terrain gradually slopes from the north to the south and from the west to the east. The higher elevation areas of the city are found in the north-northeastern and northwestern parts, with an average elevation ranging from 10 to 25 meters above sea level. These elevated areas are interspersed with hills and peaks, with the highest point being Long Binh Hill in Thu Duc district, reaching up to 32 meters.

Conversely, the low-lying areas of the city are situated in the south-southwest and southeast, with an average elevation of approximately 1 meter above sea level, and in some areas, it can be as low as 0.5 meters. The central areas, parts of Thu Duc district, Hoc Mon district, and District 12, have an average elevation ranging from 5 to 10 meters above sea level. Ho Chi Minh City is located within the geographical coordinates of 10°10' to 10°38' North latitude and 106°22' to 106°54' East longitude.

Population Size: Ho Chi Minh City is the largest city in Vietnam in terms of population and urbanization. According to the official population census as of April 1, 2009, the city had a population of 7,162,864 people, accounting for 8.34% of Vietnam's total population, with an average population density of 3,419 people per square kilometer. By 2019, the population of the city had increased to 8,993,082 people, making it the most densely populated area in Vietnam.

3.2. Assessing the Factors Influencing the Self-Organized Tourism Trend Among Young People in Ho Chi Minh City

3.2.1. Evaluation of the Reliability of the Measurement Scale

Reliability of a measurement scale refers to the extent to which the measurements of the research variables are free from errors, and the results accurately reflect the reality. To assess the reliability of the measurement scale, the research team used Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for each research concept. If a measurement variable has an item-total correlation greater than 0.3 and a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient greater than 0.6, the variable meets the requirements and is included in further analysis. The calculated Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for all factors showed that they have a reliability greater than 0.6. The coefficients ranged from 0.611 (for the "Perception of Value" factor) to 0.839 (for the "Technology Development and Application" factor). Therefore, the measurement scale used in the study demonstrates adequate reliability for subsequent analyses and testing. The variable CANHAN1 (Desire to explore and understand the cultural and natural values of the destination) was excluded due to its item-total correlation being less than 0.3, which lowered the reliability of the factor.

Table 2: Reliability Test Results

Variable Code	Total Item Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Variable Removed
The development and digital technology application		
Cronbach's Alpha = 0.839		
CN1	0.678	0.793
CN2	0.790	0.743
CN3	0.639	0.812
CN4	0.587	0.831
Characteristics of the type of tourism		
Cronbach's Alpha = 0.768		
DD1	0.434	0.865
DD2	0.672	0.610
DD3	0.721	0.546
Society		
Cronbach's Alpha = 0.698		

Variable Code	Total Item Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Variable Removed
XH1	0.466	0.643
XH2	0.438	0.661
XH3	0.586	0.572
XH4	0.449	0.657
Individual		
Cronbach's Alpha = 0.641		
CN1	0.462	0.528
CN2	0.436	0.562
CN3	0.454	0.539
Values Obtained		
Cronbach's Alpha = 0.611		
GTND1	0.410	0.526
GTND2	0.410	0.526
GTND3	0.441	0.481
Trends		
Cronbach's Alpha =0.691		
XuH1	0.539	0.558
XuH2	0.511	0.598
XuH3	0.481	0.645

Source: Data processing results from SPSS.

3.2.2. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

After evaluating the reliability through Cronbach's Alpha, variables that meet the criteria will be retained for exploratory factor analysis. Exploratory factor analysis serves as a prerequisite for linear regression analysis. To determine whether the sample size of the research survey is sufficiently large and meets the conditions, the research team conducts Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's tests.

The exploratory factor analysis of the independent variables, with a KMO test result of 0.855, and the dependent variable with a KMO result of 0.667 (falling between 0.5 and 1), along with a Bartlett's test p-value less than 0.05 (indicating that the observed variables are correlated with each other overall), allow us to conclude that the survey data meet the conditions for carrying out exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and that the results can be utilized.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test for Independent Variables

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.855
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1.148.176
	df	120
	Sig.	0.000

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's Test for Dependent Variables

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.667
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	92.548
	df	3
	Sig.	0.000

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results

The study utilized two criteria to determine the number of factors: The Kaiser criterion and the Variance Extracted criterion. Based on the processed results, the total variance extracted is 61.152%, which is greater than 50%. Therefore, the factor analysis is appropriate for the study. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) has been rotated twice. Accordingly, the observed variable CANHAN1 - Desire to experience, understand the cultural and natural values of the destination, was eliminated due to its poor quality (loading factor less than 0.5); two variables GTND1 - Experience, knowledge, skills, and GTND2 - Expanding social relationships were grouped under the factor Development and Application of Digital Technology. The complete rotated EFA results are presented as follows:

Table 5: Rotated Factor Matrix

Variable Code	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Development and Application of Digital Technology				
Extracted Variance = 36.477%				
CN2	0.845			
CN1	0.765			
CN3	0.735			
CN4	0.698			
GTND1	0.662			
GTND3	0.522			
Characteristics of the Type of Travel				
Extracted Variance = 10.753%				
DD1		0.723		
DD3		0.709		
DD2		0.692		
Social Factors				
Extracted Variance = 7.093%				
XH4			0.728	
XH1			0.651	
XH2			0.636	
XH3			0.559	
Individual Factors				
Extracted Variance = 6.83%				
CN3				0.753
CN1				0.735
CN2				0.699

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results

The EFA extracted only a single factor from the observed variables entered. The extraction of only one factor implies that the scale ensures unidimensionality, and the observed variables for the dependent variable converge quite well.

Table 6: Unrotated Matrix for Dependent Variable

Variable Code	Component
	1
XH1	0.813
XH2	0.792
XH3	0.763

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results

The results of the factor analysis of the rotation matrix with independent variables indicate the presence of 4 latent factors reflecting the self-organized travel trends of young people in Ho Chi Minh City. These factors are described as follows:

Table 7: New factor groups influencing the self-organized travel trends of young people in Ho Chi Minh City

Factor	Observable Variables	Group Name
CONGNHHE	CN1, CN2, CN3, CN4, GTND1, GTND3	Development and Application of Digital Technology
DACDIEM	DD1, DD2, DD3	Characteristics of the Type of Travel
XAHOI	XH1, XH2, XH3	Social Factors
CANHAN	CN2, CN3, CN1	Individual Factors

3.2.3. Results of Research Hypothesis Testing

Correlation Analysis Results

To assess the impact of factors on the self-organized travel trends of young people in Ho Chi Minh City, the research team used the Pearson coefficient to analyze the correlation between quantitative variables. The correlation coefficients indicate a statistically significant relationship between the dependent variable (Trends) and the independent variables (all with Sig < 0.05). Additionally, the magnitude of the correlation coefficients ensures that there is no issue of multicollinearity. Therefore, other statistical tests can be employed to examine the relationships between variables.

Table 8: Results of correlation analysis between factors in the model

		XuH	CN	DD	XH	CN
XuH	Pearson Correlation	1	0.932	0.545	0.520	0.348
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	180	180	180	180	180
CN	Pearson Correlation	0.932	1	0.602	0.528	0.324
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	180	180	180	180	180
DD	Pearson Correlation	0.545	0.602	1	0.420	0.239

	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.001
	N	180	180	180	180	180
XH	Pearson Correlation	0.520	0.528	0.420	1	0.395
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000
	N	180	180	180	180	180
CN	Pearson Correlation	0.348	0.324	0.239	0.395	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	
	N	180	180	180	180	180

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results

Results of Testing Factors Influencing the Self-Organized Travel Trends of Young People in Ho Chi Minh City

To measure the level of influence of the identified factors on the self-organized travel trends of young people in Ho Chi Minh City, the research team conducted a regression analysis based on measuring the impact of the extracted factors.

In the regression analysis model, the dependent variable is "Self-Organized Travel Trends of Young People in Ho Chi Minh City," and the independent variables are the factors extracted from the observed variables in the EFA factor analysis. The regression model is as follows:

$$XH = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{CONGNGHE} + \beta_2 \text{DACDIEM} + \beta_3 \text{XAHOI} + \beta_4 \text{CANHAN}$$

❖ Where:

XH: The value of the dependent variable - Self-Organized Travel Trends of Young People in Ho Chi Minh City

CONGNGHE: The value of the first independent variable - Development and Application of Digital Technology

DACDIEM: The value of the second independent variable - Characteristics of the Type of Travel

XAHOI: The value of the third independent variable - Social Factors

CANHAN: The value of the fourth independent variable - Individual Factors

❖ Hypotheses:

H1 - The "CONGNGHE" factor has a positive impact on the self-organized travel trends of young people in Ho Chi Minh City.

H2 - The "DACDIEM" factor has a positive impact on the self-organized travel trends of young people in Ho Chi Minh City.

H3 - The "XAHOI" factor has a positive impact on the self-organized travel trends of young people in Ho Chi Minh City.

H4 - The "CANHAN" factor has a positive impact on the self-organized travel trends of young people in Ho Chi Minh City.

Based on the investigation results below, it is observed that the F-test for the p-value (Sig) < 0.05, indicating that the model is appropriate. Additionally, the adjusted R-squared (R2) has a value of 0.87, meaning that the regression model explains 87% of the variation in the dependent variable. Thus, the model provides a high level of explanatory power.

Table 9: Regression Analysis of Factors Influencing the Self-Organized Travel Trends of Young People in Ho Chi Minh City

Model	R	R ²	R2 Adjusted	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.934	0.873	0.870	0.24913

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results

Table 10: F-Test (ANOVA)

Model	Sum square	df	Average square	F	Itself	
1	Regression	74.610	4	18.652	300.518	0.000
	Remainder	10.862	175	0.062		
	Sum	85.472	179			

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results

Table 11: Regression coefficient

Model		Unnormalized regression coefficient		Normalized regression coefficient	t	Itself.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	Constant	-0.004	0.136		-0.031	0.976
	The development and application of digital technology	0.961	0.038	0.922	25.092	0.000
	Features of the type	-0.032	0.032	-0.034	-0.990	0.324
	Social factors	0.030	0.033	0.030	0.895	0.372
	Individual Factors	0.041	0.027	0.046	1.543	0.125

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results

From the analysis results above, we can deduce the factors influencing the self-organized travel trends of young people in Ho Chi Minh City. The regression model is presented as follows:

$$XH = -0.04 + 0.961CONGNGHE - 0.32 DACDIEM + 0.3XAHOI + 0.41CANHAN$$

As a result, it can be observed that all the independent variables included in the model have a significant impact on the dependent variable, with correlation coefficients all equal to 0. Among them, the variable DACDIEM (Characteristics of Tourism Types) has a negative correlation with XH (Self-Organized Travel Trends of Young People in Ho Chi Minh City), indicating an inverse relationship between them. Furthermore, the coefficient $\beta_1 = 0.961$ implies that when the CONGNGHE factor changes by 1 unit while other factors remain constant, it results in a simultaneous change in XH by 0.961 units in the same direction. The same explanation applies to the other variables (assuming the other factors remain constant).

Therefore, based on the regression analysis results conducted above, it can be observed that the "Development and Application of Digital Technology" factor has the most significant impact on the self-organized travel trends of young people in Ho Chi Minh City, with a coefficient $\beta_1 = 0.961$. Regarding this phenomenon, as the self-organized travel trend develops, the development and application of digital technology play a crucial role. When the travel demand of young people in Ho Chi Minh City is formed, the influence of the development and application of digital technology on their desire to self-organize their trips becomes substantial. With the advancement of digital technology, young people in Ho Chi Minh City research travel destinations through travel websites and social media, book flights and accommodations, and access various travel-related services through smartphones and laptops. They use map and translation apps, among other tools. These factors significantly affect the decision to choose self-organized travel trends, and young people in Ho Chi Minh City find benefits in following this type of travel trend instead of traditional guided tours through intermediaries.

4. SOME SOLUTIONS FOR DEVELOPING THE TREND OF SELF-ORGANIZED TRAVEL AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE IN HO CHI MINH CITY

In the face of significant advancements in science and technology, businesses must constantly reinvent themselves. As society evolves, people develop diverse needs, including in the realm of tourism. Travel is no exception, and travelers are constantly changing their preferences to maximize the value they receive, all while staying within their budget. This has led to the emergence of new travel trends, including self-organized travel. In essence, self-organized travelers plan their trips independently, without the guidance of tour guides or any other travel agencies. However, this does not mean that travel companies lose their relevance. Here are some solutions that travel companies can implement to tap into the market segment of self-organized travelers. The challenge is how travel companies can remain profitable when travelers organize their trips themselves. In practice, individuals who prefer self-organized travel often struggle with planning and booking various services, such as dining, accommodation, and activities, due to a lack of information. Recognizing this, travel companies should offer comprehensive, digitally integrated self-organized travel packages. These packages should include detailed itineraries, dining options, accommodation choices, and places for experiential activities. They should also incorporate QR codes for added convenience during the traveler's journey.

Marketing plays a crucial role in business operations in general, and the travel industry is no exception. In the age of Industry 4.0, information spreads at the speed of light. Social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube are ideal channels for communication. Unlike traditional marketing, where customer needs are assessed through paper surveys or advertising products on major mass media channels, incurring significant costs, modern businesses can leverage the rapid development of technology. Travel companies should actively engage with travel communities on social media platforms where self-organized travelers gather to research needs and maximize marketing opportunities to reach customers with such preferences. Specifically, travel companies can collaborate with YouTubers, bloggers, or content creators to provide reviews and endorsements of their products, enhancing

customer trust through these third-party evaluations. These content creators need not be celebrities; the aim is to attract and build trust with customers.

Self-organized travel requires travelers to plan their itineraries and book necessary services independently. E-commerce platforms play an extremely important role in this process. Based on the findings of the factors influencing the trend of self-organized travel presented in Chapter 3, it is evident that the development and application of digital technology have the most significant impact on whether travelers opt for self-organized trips or not. Nowadays, with the application of technology, Google Maps helps travelers conquer their destinations, Traveloka offers a variety of hotel and flight deals, and numerous interactive apps engage directly with travelers during their decision-making process. Recognizing this, travel businesses need to quickly collect data on the current and potential demands of travelers. This data will help them tailor comprehensive service packages that cater to the evolving market trends as well as the specific segment of self-organized travelers.

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